

KINETIC STUDY OF THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF TIN AND SILICON TETRAMETHYLS

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The experimental results of Waring and Horton on the thermal decomposition of tin tetramethyl have been re-examined and shown to fit in better with a three-halves order rate constant and a free radical kinetic mechanism than with a unimolecular rate constant and a molecular rearrangement mechanism put forward by the authors. Also, the results of Helm and Mack on the thermal decomposition of silicon tetramethyl in the low pressure region, not amenable to first or second order kinetic expressions, have satisfactorily been interpreted in terms of three-halves order reaction involving a free radical mechanism.

With the classical work of Paneth and Hofeditz (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1335) demonstrating the presence of free radicals in the thermal decomposition of lead tetramethyl, and the illustration of the wide applicability of free radical mechanism to the kinetics of vapour phase thermal decomposition of both metal alkyls and many organic compounds (Rice and Rice, "The Aliphatic Free Radicals", 1935), attempt has been made to account even for the kinetics of the so-called quasi-unimolecular reactions in terms of atomic and free radical mechanism (Rice and Herzfeld, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 284; Pease, "Equilibrium and Kinetics of Gas Reactions", 1942). The recent investigation of the thermal decomposition of aluminium trimethyl (Yeddanapalli and Schubert, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1946, 14, 1) revealed the reaction to be kinetically of three-halves order involving a free radical mechanism, the methyl radicals resulting from the primary rupture of Al—C bond of the metal alkyl. Taylor and Cunningham (*ibid.*, 1938, 6, 357) also assumed the primary process in the thermal decomposition of mercury dimethyl to be the formation of methyl radicals which took part in subsequent reactions leading to the observed products.

In view of these facts, it was rather surprising to find that the thermal decomposition of tin tetramethyl was reported by Waring and Horton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 540) to be kinetically of first order involving not a free radical but essentially a molecular rearrangement mechanism. Another compound which had previously been reported to exhibit a unimolecular thermal decomposition above a certain initial pressure, is silicon tetramethyl (Helm and Mack, *ibid.*, 1937, 59, 60), although no attempt was made to explain the kinetics of the reaction beyond indicating the possibility of a free radical mechanism. It was thought to be of interest to re-examine the results reported on these metal alkyls from the view point of free radical mechanism.

Tin Tetramethyl

The results of Waring and Horton are presented in Table IA, in which 'r' denotes the fractional decomposition of the metal alkyl initially of a pressure of 100 mm. Hg., and *k*, the calculated unimolecular rate constant. From the rate constants at different temperatures, it was deduced that

$$\log k = 21.92 - (82,400/2.303 RT)$$

where 82,400 cal. per mol. is the activation energy E of the process. Table Ib contains the recalculated rate constants from the same experimental results on the basis of three-halves order and the corresponding integrated kinetic expression,

$$k = \frac{2}{l} \left[\frac{l}{(p_0 - p)^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{l}{p_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right]$$

in which p stands for the pressure at time l sec. and p_0 , for the initial pressure. The original values of ' r ' were transformed, for ease and simplicity of calculation, into pressures in mm. Hg. in keeping with the indicated initial pressure of 100 mm. Hg. On plotting $\log k$ against $1/T$, the slope of the line thus obtained yields for E a value of 75.9 k cal. per mol. so that the rate constant may be expressed by

$$\log k = 18.92 - (7.900/2.303 RT).$$

Comparison of Tables Ia and Ib brings out the fact that the values of k for a given temperature are much more constant in the latter than in the former case, due allowance being made for experimental errors. At higher temperatures the comparison tells even more clearly in favour of Table Ib. The recalculated E , 75.9 k cal. is substantially less than the original value 82.4 k cal., and the corrected frequency factor is about 10^{16} . Though the normal frequency factor for 1.5 order reaction is about 10^{15} (cf. Pease, *loc. cit.*, p. 133), the increased value in the present case may be presumed to be due to an increase in entropy of activation associated with the loose structure of the activated complex as compared with the reactant alkyl molecule.

The supposed unimolecular rate constant was interpreted by Waring and Horton in the sense that the metal alkyl broke down into gaseous products, of which methane formed the major constituent by molecular rearrangement thus,

Although the possibility of rupture of the Sn—C bond to give methyl radicals was recognised, it was, however, accorded only a negligible probability. The rather high value of 82.4 k cal. for E , was taken as evidence "in favour of a rearrangement mechanism for the decomposition" as against a free radical mechanism. This appears to be contrary to the generally accepted view in reaction kinetics. As Hinshelwood puts it in connection with acetaldehyde decomposition "In the decomposition of a substance such as acetaldehyde, the initial production of a free radical by a process such as $\text{CH}-\text{CHO}=\text{CH}_2 + \text{CHO}$ will require a higher activation energy than the alternative process of direct molecular rearrangement to CH_4 and CO " (Hinshelwood, "The Kinetics of Chemical Change", 1942, p. 87). Consequently the higher activation energy in the present case would seem to indicate rather a free radical mechanism, without excluding evidently the possibility of a small percentage of molecular rearrangement process also.

Proposed Free Radical Mechanism.—The free radical mechanism in the present case may be represented by the following sequence of reactions :

$\text{Sn}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ may further break down to give more methyl radicals and ultimately metallic tin. The CH_3 radicals react with metal alkyl to yield methane according to the equation,

The latter radical may, by analogy with other complex radicals, tend to lose a CH_3 and revert to a stable molecule thus,

This unsaturated product may undergo further reaction or polymerisation, thus accounting for a part of the solid deposit formed on the walls of the reaction vessel. Steps (2a) and (2b) would constitute the reaction chain leading to formation of methane as the major constituent of the gaseous products. The chain breaking process is the recombination of the methyl radicals according to equation,

TABLE IA

 $p_0 = 100 \text{ mm.}$

440°.		450°.		467.4°.		484.7°.		493.2°.	
r.	$k \cdot 10^3$	r.	$k \cdot 10^3$	r.	$k \cdot 10^3$	r.	$k \cdot 10^3$	r.	$k \cdot 10^3$
0.1250	0.3151	0.1250	1.191	0.1250	4.268	0.1250	10.86	0.1128	22.34
.1369	.3167	.1354	1.181	.1462	3.681	.1273	16.40	.1250	27.49
.2500	.3311	.2500	1.402	.2500	5.619	.2500	13.51	.2256	24.72
.2738	.3100	.2709	1.305	.2924	5.032	.2345	12.18	.2500	28.54
.4107	.2438	.4063	1.048	.4396	4.729	.3819	11.83	.3384	25.49
.5000	.2021	.5000	0.872	.5000	3.415	.5000	8.84	.4513	21.81
.5476	.1869	.5418	0.645	.5818	3.069	.5092	8.84	.5000	20.41

TABLE IB

 $p_0 = 100 \text{ mm.}$

440°.		450°.		467.4°.		484.7°.		493.2°.	
$p(\text{mm.})$	$k \cdot 10^4$	$p(\text{mm.})$	$k \cdot 10^3$	$p(\text{mm.})$	$k \cdot 10^3$	$p(\text{mm.})$	$k \cdot 10^{-3}$	$p(\text{mm.})$	$k \cdot 10^{-3}$
87.50	0.3226	87.50	0.1220	87.50	0.4368	87.50	1.1110	88.72	2.297
86.31	.3291	86.46	.1222	85.38	.3825	87.27	1.7000	87.50	2.814
75.00	.3562	75.00	.1509	75.00	.6045	75.00	1.1030	77.44	2.641
72.62	.3367	72.91	.1411	70.76	.5492	74.51	1.3090	75.00	3.068
58.93	.4677	59.37	.1195	56.14	.5499	61.81	1.3430	66.16	2.828
50.00	.2415	50.00	.1042	50.00	.4081	50.00	1.0600	54.87	2.881
45.24	.2217	45.82	.0998	41.52	.3858	49.08	1.6620	50.00	2.439

TABLE II
Decomposition of silicon tetramethyl.

Initial $p_0 = 149$ mm.					
Time. min.	Pressure (p).	$p_0 - p$.	k_1 .	k_2 .	$k_{1.5}$.
0.00	149.0	180.0			
3.25	266.0				
4.12	290.5	155.5	0.0028	0.0017	0.0008093
5.33	317.0	129.0	.0026	.00018	.0008333
6.35	334.5	111.5	.0024	.00019	.0008541
7.60	353.0	93.0	.0024	.00023	.0008874
8.78	365.0	81.0	.0020	.00027	.0008917
10.27	378.0	68.0	.0020	.00026	.0009069
11.78	387.5	58.5	.0017	.00026	.0009078
14.33	400.5	45.5	.0015	.00032	.0009230
16.78	408.3	37.7	.0013	.00031	.0009139
19.08	414.5	31.5	.0013	.00038	.0009179
22.43	419.8	26.2	.0009		.0008900
26.42	425.8	20.2	.0011		.0008989
31.10	428.7	17.3	.0006		
97.0	446.0 = p_0				

Applying the steady state principle, the concentration of methyl radicals may be calculated in the following manner :

$$\begin{aligned} d[\text{CH}_3]/dt &= k_1[\text{A}] - k_2[\text{CH}_3][\text{CH}_3] = 0 \\ [\text{CH}_3] &= (k_1/k_2)^{1/2}[\text{A}]^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

in which A denotes the metal alkyl and k 's the rate constants of the steps indicated by the appropriate subscripts. The overall rate of disappearance of the metal alkyl is given by

$$-d[\text{A}]/dt = k_1[\text{A}] + k_2(k_1/k_2)^{1/2}[\text{A}]^{3/2}.$$

Assuming the initial reaction constant k_1 to be negligible compared to that of the chain process, the overall decomposition rate is seen to be proportional to alkyl concentration raised to three-halves power, in agreement with the revised kinetic order of the reaction (cf. Table I B).

Step (2a), a radical-molecule reaction, with a relatively small activation energy, 15 k cal. or less, is of rapid occurrence and accounts for the high proportion of methane formed. The small percentages, 5 to 10, of ethylene and hydrogen may be accounted for partly by the dissociation of ethane and partly by the breakdown of the metal alkyl molecules directly according to the equations,

as suggested by Waring and Horton (*loc. cit.*).

The activation energy will be governed essentially by the energy needed to break the Sn—C bond for which no experimental data are at present available and need not be considered further.

Silicon Tetramethyl

The thermal decomposition of silicon tetramethyl investigated by Helm and Mack (*loc. cit.*) in the temperature range of 659°–717° was found to be homogeneous and of first order above an initial pressure of 149 mm. Below this, however, the unimolecular character could not be observed, as can be seen from the results in Table II in which column 2 gives pressures p of the system at various times of reaction, the initial pressure p_0 being 149 mm. Hg., column 3 gives the difference between p and p_∞ (pressure at complete decomposition) and columns 4 and 5 list the first and second order constants calculated by Helm and Mack, the last column presenting the 1.5 order constants calculated by us according to the integrated kinetic expression given above.

It is evident from Table II that the values of k in the last column are practically constant within experimental errors over the whole pressure range, whereas those in the two preceding columns do not show such constancy. It is not unreasonable therefore to conclude that the kinetic order of the reaction is three-halves within the indicated pressure range. The products of reaction have been reported to consist mostly of methane (about 60%) and hydrogen (about 40%) with minute amounts of olefines and acetylenes. From the similarity of these products with those obtained from pyrolysis of ethane (Bone and Coward, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1206), the authors suggested the reaction mechanism to be similar in both cases, involving probably methyl radicals as intermediates, without, however, attempting to elaborate such a free radical mechanism. We are therefore tentatively presenting a comprehensive free radical mechanism capable of accounting for the fractional order of reaction at pressures below 149 mm. (cf. Table II) but also for the first order character of the reaction at higher pressures, substantiated in the original paper.

Proposed Reaction Mechanism.—The initial step may be considered to be the breaking of one of the Si—C bonds of the alkyl,

the complex radical possibly breaking down to give more methyl radicals and finally Si. The methyl radicals react with alkyl molecules to give methane thus,

The complex radical may be assumed to break down into methyl and ethyl radicals, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5 + 2\text{CH}_3 + \text{Si}$, the C_2H_5 undergoing further decomposition,

and the H atoms reacting with alkyl molecules yielding the next major product after methane, namely, gaseous hydrogen according to the equation,

This complex radical will undergo the change already indicated. At higher alkyl pressures, there is the possibility of an adduct between methyl radicals and alkyl molecules of the type indicated below, justification for which may be found in the recent paper of Noyes, Jr. and Gomer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3390),

where X stands for the complex adduct which may then react with a methyl radical according to the equation,

these two steps forming the chain ending processes at higher alkyl pressures. At lower alkyl pressures, the methyl radicals may interact mutually to give ethane,

Now to account for 1.5 order below 149 mm. pressure of alkyl, steps 1 to 4 and 7 are to be taken for the reasons just given. Applying the steady state principle and representing the alkyl by A, the concentrations of the appropriate active species are found to be expressed by,

$$[CH_3] = (k_1/k_7)^{\frac{1}{2}}[A]^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ and } [II] = (k_2/k_4)(k_1/k_7)^{\frac{1}{2}}[A]^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

The overall rate of decomposition of the alkyl is given by,

$$-d[A]/dt = k_1[A] + k_2[CH_3][A] + k_4[II][A]$$

which on substituting for the active species, becomes

$$-d[A]/dt = k_1[A] + 2k_2(k_1/k_7)^{\frac{1}{2}}[A]^{\frac{3}{2}}.$$

Neglecting the slow initial reaction in comparison with the chain reaction steps, the overall rate is seen to be proportional to the concentration of the alkyl raised to power 1.5 in agreement with the recalculated order for the results given in Table II.

At initial pressures higher than 149 mm. Hg., the sequence of reaction steps to be taken into account, for reasons already adduced, are 1 to 6 inclusively. Calculations similar to the ones given above lead, for the overall rate of disappearance of alkyl, to the expression,

$$-d[A]/dt = k_1[A] + 2k_1k_2/(k_2 + 2k_3) \cdot [A].$$

Neglecting as before k_1 for reasons already given, the overall rate of decomposition of the alkyl is proportional to its simple concentration, and the reaction is therefore of first order, as actually observed by Helm and Mack (*loc. cit.*).

The above mechanism accounts for the reaction products being mainly methane and hydrogen, the ethane formed by the chain breaking steps, small in amount, being decomposed at the high temperature of the reaction. Nothing definite can be said about the activation energy of the three-halves order reaction since data are available only at one temperature. As a part of a comprehensive programme of research on the decomposition of metal alkyls, it is proposed to make a thorough investigation of the above two alkyls in order to be able to secure a more complete picture of their reaction kinetics.